

The role of constituents on the compressive strength of composites

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The Composites Centre
for research, modelling, testing and training in advanced composites

Goals

- ➔ Enabling material development
- ➔ Increase accuracy of models
- ➔ Identify gaps in characterisation

Longitudinal compressive failure

➔ Kink-band formation:

- Fibre misalignments
- Matrix shear response

Outline

- ➔ Properties of the matrix
 - Shear non-linearity
 - Plasticity parameters
- ➔ Properties of the fibres
 - Shear (& transverse) modulus
- ➔ Properties of interface
 - Matrix- vs. interface- dominated failure
 - Interfacial shear strength
- ➔ Conclusions

FE models for compressive failure

Fibre/matrix **unit cell** with periodic BCs

misalignment geometry: *Paluch (1996)*

T300 **carbon** fibres

- Non-linear elastic longitudinal response
- Transversely isotropic

Epoxy matrix (Epon 862)

- Non-linear shear response
- Drucker-Prager plasticity

Global stress-strain curve

Matrix evolution at max. misalign.

Longitudinal fibre compression fields

Matrix shear constitutive law

Matrix shear stress (MPa)

Matrix shear strain (%)

Composite compressive strength

Composite strength (MPa)

matrix non-linearity in shear

Friction angle

➡ Controls **tension/compression/shear** asymmetry

➡ Matrix under complex 3D stress state

Dilation angle

➡ Controls volumetric strains ("dilation") during plastic deformation

➡ Fibres constrain matrix dilation during plasticity

Effect on composite strength

Composite strength (MPa)

Apparent constitutive law

Matrix von Mises stress (MPa)

Effect on composite strength

Composite strength (MPa)

Hydrostatic pressure at peak

Matrix hydrostatic pressure (MPa)

Non-linear longitudinal response

Compressive stress (GPa)

Transversely isotropic (linear)

➔ Baseline elastic constants:

Csanádi et al. (2017)

$$E_{22}^f = E_{33}^f = 27.6 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{12}^f = G_{13}^f = 10.9 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu^f = 0.3$$

Effect on composite's shear modulus

Composite shear modulus (GPa)

Effect on composite strength

Composite strength (MPa)

Hydrostatic pressure at peak

Matrix hydrostatic pressure (MPa)

Cohesive element modelling

Cohesive properties

- ➔ Same shear modulus & strength as matrix
- ➔ Fracture toughness: 2-10 J/m² (no influence), *Zhou et al. (2018)*
- ➔ Failure initiation & propagation: quadratic interaction

Interfacial shear strength

➔ Experimental data for same composite

➔ Huge experimental uncertainty!

With vs. without interface

Longitudinal compressive stress (MPa)

Effect on composite strength

Composite strength (vs. model without interface)

Fractography

➔ Does interfacial failure really prevent plasticity in the matrix?

"Band of out-of-plane microbuckling"
(Greenhalgh, 2009)

Equivalent plastic strains in matrix

➔ **Without interface**, peak stress (3)

➔ **With interface**, interfacial failure (4)

➔ Matrix:

- Plasticity

Materials: confinement & strengthening

Characterisation: friction & dilation angles

- Shear non-linearity

Characterisation: include strain @ peak

Models: beware of LE-PP assumption
& strain localisation

➔ Fibres:

Materials: increase shear stiffness

Models: account for finite shear stiffness

Characterisation: shear modulus

➔ Interfaces:

Characterisation: IFSS (consistency) &
complex 3D loading

Models: are CZM adequate?

"Pure shear and compression-shear
characterisation of polymer matrix..."

Bohao Zhang

Wednesday 2nd, 3.20 pm

"Experimental characterisation
of the **dilation angle** of polymers"

Gustavo Quino Quispe

Thursday 3rd, 10.00 am

**Next
COMP**

Next Generation
Fibre-Reinforced Composites

<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

I would like to acknowledge funding which supported this work from the UK Research and Innovation - EPSRC Programme Grant; Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites: A Full Scale Redesign for Compression (EP/T011653/1)

A collaboration between Imperial College London and University of Bristol

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